

Questionnaire for Evaluating Learning Experiences in Engineering AI-Enabled Systems

AI Algorithms: Theory and Engineering;
University of Bremen (Winter Semester 2024/25)

Authors: Amir Mashmool; Kishan Ravindra Sawant; Nico Hochgeschwender
Affiliation: University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany
Contact: [mashmool.amir, kishan.sawant, nico.hochgeschwender]@uni-bremen.de
Version: 1.0
Date: January 29, 2026

Dear Participant,

Thank you for your interest in participating in this survey regarding your insights on the course “*AI Algorithms — Theory and Engineering.*” The purpose of this survey is to gather feedback on your academic background and learning experience throughout this project-based course in order to improve its structure and teaching methods.

In this survey, you will be asked to provide information about your Bachelor’s degree, your expertise in Software Engineering (e.g., requirements engineering, software architecture, and programming), and your knowledge of machine learning (ML)-based methods, tools, and frameworks. In addition, we seek your reflections on key learnings related to Software Engineering, Machine Learning, and the development of scalable software architectures.

Please note:

- The data collected will be used solely for academic and research purposes.
- No personal identifying data will be stored, aside from general demographic information.
- Participation is voluntary, and you may discontinue at any time.
- All responses will remain anonymous, and no identifying information will be shared outside of the study.
- The survey will take approximately 20 minutes to complete.

Your insights will contribute to improving the course and curriculum for future students. Thank you for your valuable input.

Consent Statement

I have read the description of this survey and voluntarily agree to participate. I understand that the results will be anonymized and may be published in scientific papers.

By selecting ‘Yes,’ I confirm my consent to participate in this survey. I understand that my responses will remain confidential and will only be used for research purposes.

Do you agree to participate? Yes No

Table 1: Questionnaire

#	Question
Background in software engineering	
Q1	Name of your bachelor's degree
Q2	Years of experience as software developer before taking the course <1 <input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 >=4
Q3	List projects where you've designed software architecture
Q4	List learning-enabled projects that you developed before taking the course
Q5	Past experience with requirement engineering vspacelmm <input type="checkbox"/> Used in one or more projects <input type="checkbox"/> Not used before this course
Q6	List the tools and frameworks you've used before this course that you used in the project. This can also include tools for learning and deployment of software systems (e.g., Docker, Flask, etc.)
Learning from the course	
Q7	What is the most important takeaway from the course from the perspective of software engineering?
Q8	What was the most challenging aspect of the project from the perspective of software engineering?
Q9	What is the most important takeaway from the course from the perspective of machine learning (ML)?
Q10	What was the most challenging aspect of the project from the perspective of ML?
Q11	What is the most important takeaway from the course regarding integrating ML methodology with software architecture?
Q12	What was the most challenging aspect of the project from the perspective of integration and deployment?
Q13	Architecture Trade-off Analysis Method (ATAM) was helpful in making design decisions Fully agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 Fully disagree
Q14	What are the two major challenges you faced due to changes in requirements (either from within the team or from assignments)?
Q15	Did you have to make any significant changes in the system architecture due to evolving requirements? If so, what changes were necessary?

Table 1 (continued)

Q16	<p>If you were to implement similar projects from scratch in the future, how would you prioritize the following architectural considerations and software engineering practices to ensure the system can easily adapt to evolving requirements?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Comparison of existing architectures, ML models, and datasets <input type="checkbox"/> Less priority <input type="checkbox"/> Medium priority <input type="checkbox"/> High priority <input type="checkbox"/> Critical priority Modular software design <input type="checkbox"/> Less priority <input type="checkbox"/> Medium priority <input type="checkbox"/> High priority <input type="checkbox"/> Critical priority Requirement engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Less priority <input type="checkbox"/> Medium priority <input type="checkbox"/> High priority <input type="checkbox"/> Critical priority Trade-off analysis (e.g., ATAM) <input type="checkbox"/> Less priority <input type="checkbox"/> Medium priority <input type="checkbox"/> High priority <input type="checkbox"/> Critical priority Documentation of evolving requirements <input type="checkbox"/> Less priority <input type="checkbox"/> Medium priority <input type="checkbox"/> High priority <input type="checkbox"/> Critical priority Establishing best software development practices (e.g., versioning, automated testing, CI/CD) <input type="checkbox"/> Less priority <input type="checkbox"/> Medium priority <input type="checkbox"/> High priority <input type="checkbox"/> Critical priority
Q17	<p>Rate the exposure that you had in these stages of development</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Modular pipeline development <input type="checkbox"/> No exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Less exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfiable exposure <input type="checkbox"/> High exposure Feature extraction and data integration <input type="checkbox"/> No exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Less exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfiable exposure <input type="checkbox"/> High exposure Design decisions via ATAM <input type="checkbox"/> No exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Less exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfiable exposure <input type="checkbox"/> High exposure Adaptation to evolving requirements <input type="checkbox"/> No exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Less exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfiable exposure <input type="checkbox"/> High exposure Validation and evaluation <input type="checkbox"/> No exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Less exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfiable exposure <input type="checkbox"/> High exposure Deployment and regular model updates <input type="checkbox"/> No exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Less exposure <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfiable exposure <input type="checkbox"/> High exposure
Q18	<p>What tools and frameworks did you learn during the course apart from the ones that you already used before?</p>
Course evaluation	

Table 1 (continued)

Q19	<p>To what degree do you think each of the following objectives were achieved in this course?</p> <p>1. Understand the role of ML components in larger systems and the challenges of engineering beyond accuracy <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree</p> <p>2. Understand the importance of formal specifications in learning-enabled systems, and how to use them to devise validation <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree</p> <p>3. Summarize the distinct goals and challenges faced by software engineers versus data scientists <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree</p> <p>4. Decompose large-scale AI systems into smaller architectural units and employ methods to ensure multi-dimensional quality, including safety, ethics, and transparency <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree</p>
Q20	<p>Significance of mid-term presentations</p> <p>Not helpful <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 Very helpful</p>
Q21	<p>What is one major aspect of the course (in the curriculum, lab, or assignments) that you think should be kept, and what is one aspect that could be improved?</p>
Q22	<p>Rate the level of difficulty of the course</p> <p>Easier to follow up <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 It was a lot of effort</p>